

Detailed protocol: Isolation of Generative Cells from mature pollen grains

1. Pollen collection

- Collect mature pollen grains by gently vibrating 3–4 flowers at anthesis to a glass Petri dish.
- Vibration to release pollen can be achieved by gently touching the flower peduncle with a vibrating object (we use a tissue ruptor from Qiagen, an electrical toothbrush may also be used). Alternatively, use small forceps to remove the anthers and tap them into a glass Petri dish to release the pollen.

2. Add glass beads

- Transfer the collected pollen to a microcentrifuge tube and add approximately 150 μ l of glass beads (425–600 μ m, Sigma).

3. Add buffer

- Add 500 μ l of ice-cold sperm cell buffer (Santos et al., 2017) containing:
 - 1.3 mM H_3BO_3
 - 3.6 mM $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
 - 0.74 mM KH_2PO_4
 - 438 mM Sucrose
 - 7 mM MOPS
 - 0.83 mM $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$
 - Adjust pH to 6.0

4. Disrupt pollen wall

- Vortex the tube at 2200 rpm for 2 minutes to break the pollen wall and release the pollen content, including generative cells.

5. Filter and isolate Generative Cells

- Filter the supernatant through a 15 μ m mesh using a CellTrics® filtering system into a 2 ml microcentrifuge tube.
- Centrifuge briefly (5 seconds) to pass the solution through the mesh to exclude debris.

6. Place the he Generative Cell suspension on ice, the sample is ready for FACS.

Detailed protocol: Isolation of Sperm Cells from semi-*in vivo* grown pollen tubes

1. Emasculation

- Emasculate closed flower buds 72 hours before anthesis by carefully removing the conic anthers with fine forceps (see Detailed Protocol Figure 1A).

2. Pollen collection

- After 72 hours, collect fresh pollen from 8–10 flowers as described above and store it in a glass Petri dish.

3. Collect emasculated pistils

- Remove the sepals and collect emasculated pistils by holding them at the stalk.
- Place the pistils on a glass slide with the ovary fixed on the edge of the double-sided tape (see Detailed Protocol Figure 1B).

4. Inspect pistils

- Using a stereomicroscope, check the pistils for damage and confirm that the stigma is receptive (appears glossy). Discard any damaged or non-receptive pistils.

5. Pollination

- Dip the receptive stigmas into the freshly collected pollen to pollinate them (see Detailed Protocol Figure 1C).

6. Excise pollinated pistils

- Fix the pollinated pistils on the glass slide with double-sided tape.
- Excise the pistils at the junction of the style and ovary with a sharp needle (the cut must be fast and clean to avoid squashing the style base).

7. Semi-*in vivo* assembly

- Gently place the excised pistils along the edge of a 35 mm imaging Petri dish (MatTek) containing 40 μ l of freshly pre-prepared pollen germination medium:
 - 0.2 mM $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
 - 0.1 mM KNO_3
 - 0.2 mM MgSO_4
 - 0.2 mM H_3BO_3
 - 10% Sucrose
 - 1% Casein
- Ensure the cut end of the style is in direct contact with the medium (see Detailed Protocol Figure 1D).

8. Incubation

- Cover the Petri dish with its lid, lined with wet paper to maintain humidity.
- Place the dish in a humid chamber and incubate at 25°C for 17.5 hours.

9. Pollen tube burst and cell release

- After incubation, remove the pollen germination medium by pipetting.
- Replace it with 40 µl of burst solution containing:
 - 0.45 M Mannitol
 - 0.5% Cellulase
 - 0.3% Macerozyme R-10
 - 0.05% Pectolyase Y-23
- Incubate the dish at 25°C for 30 minutes.
- Pipette the solution up and down gently to ensure the collection of most of the sperm cells.

11. Collect cell suspension

- Transfer the released cell suspension into a collection tube containing a 15 µm mesh using a CellTrics® filtering system.
- Optionally, repeat the mixing step with an additional 50 µl of sperm cell buffer to maximize recovery of sperm cells.

12. Add extraction buffer

- Add 400 µl of ice-cold sperm extraction buffer to the collected suspension.

13. Filter and isolate Sperm Cells

- Filter the suspension through a 15 µm mesh by brief centrifugation (5 seconds) to exclude debris.

14. Place the Sperm Cell suspension on ice, the sample is ready for FACS.

Detailed Protocol Figure 1: Preparation of semi-*in vivo* grown pollen tubes for sperm cell isolation. A) Flower emasculating: the conic anthers are removed with a fine forceps from closed flower buds 72 hours before anthesis; B) Collection of emasculated pistils: at the anthesis day, emasculated pistils are collected and placed by the stalk on double side tape; C) Pollination: the pistil stigma is dipped in pollen and placed back on the double side tape, the style is then cut at the ovary base (dashed line panel B); D) Placement of pollinated pistil in medium: cut pollinated pistils are gently placed inside the germination medium with the style base in direct contact with the medium. Scale bar is 1 cm.